

THE ROLE OF ACCURACY AND FLUENCY IN TEACHING SPEAKING.

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Teaching speaking is a very important part of second language learning. The ability to communicate in a second language clearly and efficiently contributes to the success of the learner in school and success later in every phase of life. By One problem that students often have is speaking fluently. This is common when lessons have focused on grammar and where speaking activities have been limited to drills or tightly controlled pairwork activities. In this article, I'll take a closer look at developing fluency in speaking and provide some activities to help. The dictionary* definitions for the word fluent are 1) able to speak a (foreign) language very well without difficulty; 2) expressing yourself in a clear and confident way, without seeming to make an effort. For many learners the words 'without difficulty', 'in a clear and confident way', and 'without seeming to make an effort' are all issues. It is important to remember that speed is not part of any of the definitions and nor is accuracy, unless of course you take 'speak a language very well' to imply that this means without mistakes. If you think about it, even native speakers of a language make mistakes and yet you would usually call them fluent speakers. How fast you speak is also not a clear indicator of fluency. If you speak quickly, but lack confidence, and don't express yourself clearly, are you any more fluent than someone who speaks slowly but effortlessly? No. So ultimately fluency is about confidence, effort and ease. One of the main reasons is lack of confidence. They might know what they want to say in their head, but actually producing it is something else. Students need to develop confidence in their ability to say what they want to say and to communicate effectively. Another reason is that often in a classroom everything a student says is scrutinized for mistakes. This not only affects their confidence, but also means that they spend time running through the words in their head before opening their mouth. Quite clearly then, two of the most important things to focus on when developing fluency are giving students confidence and enabling them to communicate their ideas and thoughts. Obviously, the best way to help students become more fluent is to give them plenty of practice. However, practice alone is not enough as they may not take all the opportunities offered. If we go back to why students find it difficult to be fluent, there were two main reasons. If we deal with these reasons, then this will certainly improve their

chances. So, the first thing is to remember what the purpose of any fluency speaking task is. It is not to be 100% accurate and correct. If we, the teacher, focus on student's mistakes and keep on correcting them, then they will lose any confidence they had, stop talking and the whole activity will fail. On the other hand, should we ignore all mistakes? Probably not. But there is a time and place to deal with these. I'll look more closely at this issue in the next section. Another thing that is important is that we don't make students go into an activity 'cold'. What I mean by this is that students aren't asked just to speak without any time to collect their thoughts. Effective planning time will lead to a far more effective speaking activity and will help build students' confidence. Finally, it's essential that the activity you set is meaningful. Students won't be able to speak about something that doesn't interest them, or isn't relevant to them. It's quite useful to get students to suggest topics that interest them as they are more likely to contribute to the speaking activity. In the classroom, when planning a speaking activity, consider whether you will be assessing your students on accuracy or fluency and stick to that decision. If you choose to focus on fluency, don't stop your students if they make mistakes but if you are aiming for accuracy then make sure your students are producing accurate language. In a nutshell, both accuracy and fluency are important in the classroom and one should not be sacrificed for the other. This may sound simple and logical, but it's easy to try to incorporate elements of both accuracy and fluency into your lessons, often with the result that your students don't get the benefit of practising either. Instead, make sure there are opportunities for both types of activities in your lessons to ensure your students get the best of both worlds and get practice with both accuracy and fluency.

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